

A STUDY ON CONSUMERS' PRODUCT PREFERENCE AND SATISFACTION ON ONLINE SHOPPING

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Abstract:

Online shopping is the activity of buying and selling of goods and services over the internet. In the era of modernistic and with the wonderful expansion of social media, various businesses have globalized their sales through internet. Over the decades the maximum of business organizations have been providing various products like electronic items, cosmetics, apparels, books, toys, household appliances, foot wears, etc., to their customers through online. Even non-durable goods and medicines are also marketed through online. Online shopping is a technological tool for better marketing performance. In a competitive world, people are getting busy with their own work and they don't find time for shopping. Online shopping saves their time a lot, as they can do it from their home or at workplace. This study made an attempt to find out the products preferred by consumers on online shopping and to know about the consumers' level of satisfaction on online shopping. The study was conducted among 121 experienced online shopping consumers based on convenience sampling method. Simple percentage and Chi-square test are used to analyze the collected data. The results indicate that most of the consumers are students and they are most interested to buy electronic items through online shopping. Majority of the consumers are satisfied with quality of product and procedure on online shopping.

Key Words: Online Shopping, Globalized Business, Product Preference & Satisfaction

Introduction:

Internet is the fastest growing media during the past decade. Especially online shopping is the process whereby consumers directly buy goods/services from a seller, without intermediary. Through online shopping, different type of business and organizations has gained a tremendous opportunity to increase their sale and to maintain a direct relationship with its customers. The increasing use of internet by the young generation in India provides an emerging prospect for online retailers. Unlike traditional marketing, online marketing has many advantages like global reach, availability of wide choices and cheaper products, 24X7 timing etc.

Declining broadband subscription prices and the launch of 4G service have become the driving forces of e-commerce in India. From buying groceries to furniture, from apparel to accessories, and beauty products and bijouterie to ticketing, online shopping has greatly empowered the Indian consumer. The online shopping is rapidly changing with evolving trends and an increasing number of online consumers. Morgan Stanley, a financial services firm estimated that by the year 2020, India will have 320 million online shoppers. That is 6.4 times more than in the year 2015. According to digital payments platform PayPal and market research firm Ipsos, the overall online sales is expected to touch Rs. 8,75,600 crore in 2018 from the estimated Rs. 4,92,500 crore in 2016.

Review of Literature:

Anh Kim Dang et.al (2018), found that female consumers who have difficulty in doing usual household activities were more likely to purchase food products through online. The study also suggests that seeking online food products among consumers was most influenced by online interactions, particularly by peers. Jadhav and Khanna (2016), identified that availability, promotions, low price, convenience, comparison, customer service, attitude, perceived ease of use, time consciousness and trust are the major influencing factors for online shopping. Rajesh Iyer and Eastman (2014), revealed that the consumers who are more educated, knowledgeable and aware of the technology and those who have a positive attitude towards online shopping are much more interested in purchasing of goods through online.

Masoud (2013), in his study found that the perceived risks like financial, product delivery and information were negatively affected the online shopping behavior of consumers. He also suggests that there was no significant effect of time and social risk on online shopping among consumers. Charles et.al (2010), examined the young women's online shopping behavior and found that young women's perceived enjoyment and usefulness of social e-shopping was greater than that of traditional e-shopping. Vijay, Sai and Balaji (2009), found that convenience and time saving drive consumers to shop online, while security and privacy concerns put

off them from doing so. According to Miyazaki and Fernandez (2000), the majority of consumers pay more attention to the privacy and it will increase difficulty of making decision during the online shopping.

Statement of the Problem:

In the competitive business world, consumers' satisfaction is the prime factor to attract and retain the consumers. Consumer satisfaction with respect to online shopping is the extent to which consumer's perception of the online experience confirms their expectation. Consumers decide whether, what, when, from whom, where and how much to buy. Youngsters are mostly using the internet and access internet on regular basis. Due to the vast usage of internet, the buying patterns of consumers have been changed. It has changed the way goods are purchased and sold, resulting to the exponential growth in the number of online consumers. Consumers' attitude towards online shopping and willing to shop on online are not only affected by convenience and enjoyment but also by other factors like consumer individuality, product distinctiveness, previous online shopping experience and faith in online shopping. The present study made an attempt to identify the attitude of consumer while buying different products through online.

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives of the study.

- ✓ To find out the most preferred product by the consumers on online shopping.
- ✓ To know about the consumers level of satisfaction on online shopping.

Research Methodology:

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data. Secondary data was collected through various journals, newspapers, websites, magazines, etc., Primary data was collected through structured questionnaire. The questionnaire contains questions relating to socio-economic profile of respondents, level of awareness and satisfaction on online shopping. Pollachi taluk was selected as study area. The required data was collected by applying convenience sampling method. Of the total 150 questionnaires issued, only 121 questionnaires were collected and taken for analysis. Collected data has been analyzed by using simple percentage and chi-square test.

Summary of Findings:

Demographic Details of the Respondents:

The findings relating to demographic details of sample consumers namely gender, age, marital status and occupation are presented below.

Table 1: Demographic detail of the respondents

Demographic Factor	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	44	36
Female	77	64
Total	121	100
Age		
Upto 20 Years	28	23
21 - 30 Years	58	48
31 - 40 Years	18	15
Above 40 Years	17	14
Total	121	100
Marital Status		
Married	36	30
Unmarried	85	70
Total	121	100
Occupation		
Students	61	51
Private Employees	33	28
Government Employees	19	16
Business persons	8	5
Total	121	100

Table 1 reveals that out of 121 respondents, 36 percentage of the respondents are male and remaining 64 percentage of respondents are female. Further 23 percentage of the respondents belonged to the age group of upto 20 years, 48 percentage of the respondents belonged to the age group of 21-30 years, 15 percentage and 14 percentage of the total respondents belonged to the age groups of 31-40 years and above 40 years respectively. 30 percentage of the respondents are married while 70 percentage of the respondents are unmarried. 51 percentage of the respondents are students and 28 percentage of the respondents are private employees. Merely

16 percentage of the respondents are government employees, whereas 5 percentage of the respondents are doing business.

Products Preferred by the Respondents:

The table below depicts that the classification of respondents based on product preference on online shopping.

It is identified that 48(40%) respondents are most interested to buy electronic items through online shopping, 32(26%) respondents are like to buy cosmetics through online shopping, 19(16%) respondents are buy footwear through online shopping, 9(7%) respondents are like to buy apparels on online shopping and 13(11%) respondents interested to purchase books through online shopping.

Table 2: Products preferred by the respondents

Products	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Electronic Items	48	40
Cosmetics	32	26
Footwear	19	16
Apparels	9	7
Books	13	11
Total	121	100

Exhibit 1: Products preferred by the respondents

Satisfaction on Online Shopping:

The following hypotheses were framed and analyzed by using Chi-Square test to know the satisfaction level of the consumers about online shopping.

i) Area and Level of Satisfaction on Door Delivery:

Ho1 = There exists no significant association between area of the respondents and level of satisfaction on door delivery.

Table 3: Area and level of satisfaction on door delivery

Area	Level of satisfaction			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Urban	2(4%)	17 (37%)	27 (59%)	46 (100%)
Rural	5(7%)	27 (36%)	43 (57%)	75 (100%)
Total	7	44	70	121

Degree of freedom = 2, Calculated χ^2 value = 0.281, Table value @ 5% = 5.991

The percentage of consumers with high level of satisfaction on door delivery is high with urban area consumers and the percentage of consumers with low level of satisfaction on door delivery is high with rural area consumers. Since the calculated χ^2 value (0.281) is less than the table value (5.991) at 5% level. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between area of the respondents and their level of satisfaction on door delivery.

ii) Age and Level of Satisfaction on Availability of Products:

Ho2 = There is no significant association between age group of the respondents and level of satisfaction on availability products.

Table 4: Age and level of satisfaction on availability of products

Age	Level of Satisfaction			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Upto 20 years	0 (0%)	18 (64%)	10 (36%)	28 (100%)
21-30 years	5 (9%)	29 (50%)	24 (41%)	58 (100%)
31-40 years	1 (6%)	9 (50%)	8 (44%)	18 (100%)

Above 40 years	3 (18%)	7 (41%)	7 (41%)	17 (100%)
Total	9	63	49	121

Degree of freedom = 6, Calculated χ^2 value = 6.153, Table value @ 5% = 12.592

The percentage of consumers with high level of satisfaction on availability of products is high with the age group of 31-40 years and the percentage of consumers with low level of satisfaction on availability of products is high with the age group of above 40 years. Since the calculated χ^2 value (6.153) is less than the table value (12.592) at 5% level. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore it is found that there is no significant association between age of the respondents and their level of satisfaction on availability of products.

iii) Gender and Level of Satisfaction on Product Quality:

Ho3 = There is no significant association between gender of the respondents and level of satisfaction on product quality.

Table 5: Gender and level of satisfaction on product quality

Gender	Level of satisfaction			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Male	10 (23%)	26 (59%)	8 (18%)	44 (100%)
Female	4 (5%)	58 (75%)	15 (20%)	77 (100%)
Total	14	84	23	121

Degree of freedom = 2, Calculated χ^2 value = 8.527, Table value @ 5% = 5.991

The percentage of consumers with high level of satisfaction on product quality is high with female and the percentage of consumer with low level of satisfaction on product quality is high with male. Since the calculated χ^2 value (8.527) is greater than the table value (5.991) at 5% level. Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is identified that there is significant association between gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction on product quality.

iv) Marital Status and Level of Satisfaction on Product Comparison and Selection:

Ho4 = There is no significant association between marital status of the respondents and level of satisfaction on product comparison and selection.

Table 6: Marital status and level of satisfaction on product comparison and selection

Marital Status	Level of satisfaction			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Married	6 (17%)	18 (50%)	12 (33%)	36 (100%)
Unmarried	12 (14%)	47 (55%)	26 (31%)	85 (100%)
Total	18	65	38	121

Degree of freedom = 2, Calculated χ^2 value = 0.303, Table value @ 5% = 5.991

The percentage of consumers with high level of satisfaction on product comparison and selection is high with who are married and the percentage of consumers with low level of satisfaction on product comparison and selection is also high with who are married. Since the calculated χ^2 value (0.303) is less than the table value (5.991) at 5% level. Hence, Null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between marital status of the respondents and their level of satisfaction on product comparison and selection.

v) Experience and Level of Satisfaction on Online Shopping Procedure:

Ho5 = There is no significant association between experience in online shopping and level of satisfaction on online shopping procedure.

Table 7: Experience and level of satisfaction on online shopping procedure

Experience Level	Level of satisfaction			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Below 1 year	15 (29%)	15 (29%)	22 (42%)	52 (100%)
1-3 years	4 (6%)	41 (65%)	18 (29%)	63 (100%)
Above 3 years	0 (0%)	2 (46%)	4 (54%)	6 (100%)
Total	19	58	44	121

Degree of freedom = 4, Calculated χ^2 value = 21.328, Table value @ 1% = 13.277

The percentage of consumers with high level of satisfaction on online shopping procedure is high with consumers who have experience of above three years and the percentage of consumers with low level of satisfaction on online shopping procedure is high with consumers who have experience of below one year. Since the calculated χ^2 value (21.328) is greater than the table value (13.277) at 1% level. Hence, Null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is found that there is highly significant association between experience in online shopping and level of satisfaction on online shopping procedure.

Suggestions:

Based on the findings of the study and the opinion given by the respondents during data collection, the following suggestions are given.

- ✓ Make websites more lively using video and chart about the product.
- ✓ Personal details furnished during transactions should be kept confidential.
- ✓ Delivery charges may be reduced.
- ✓ Make it easy for customers to contact customer care.
- ✓ The complaints raised by the customers should be effectively managed and proper action should be taken in time.

Conclusion:

Online shopping has greatly impacted the purchasing pattern of the consumers. There is a wide range of products and consumers from all around the world can buy any products at any time. The study concluded that maximum of online consumers are youngsters and they are mostly preferred to buy electronic items. The study also found that there is an association between gender of the respondents and quality of the product on online shopping. Procedure on online shopping is a simple to the consumers who have more number of years experience in online shopping. The study suggests that better understanding of consumers on online shopping will help companies in getting more consumers and increasing their online business revenues.

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